

Multi-phase homogenization procedure for estimating the mechanical properties of shot-earth materials

M. Baccocchi^{1,2,*}, V. Savino³, L. Lanzoni^{2,4}, A.M. Tarantino^{2,4}, M. Viviani³

Abstract

The paper proposes an analytical homogenization procedure to predict the overall elastic properties of shot-earth, a sustainable composite material made of local excavated soil, aggregates and, if needed, a binder for stabilization. A multi-step methodology based on the Mori-Tanaka approach is used to account for the stabilized soil inclusions. This approach is proposed in order to shorten the mix-design procedures and readily provide to the structural engineers a set of mechanical properties of the shot-earth components to be used in the early design phases, when the construction field is not open yet and excavation of the site has not begun. The analytical results were successfully validated through an experimental campaign.

Keywords: Shot-earth materials, Homogenization, Sustainable materials, Mori-Tanaka scheme, Experimental validation

*corresponding author

¹DESD-Department of Economics, Science and Law, University of San Marino, San Marino

²CRICT-Centro di Ricerca Interdipartimentale Costruzioni e del Territorio, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, 41125 Modena, Italy

³HEIG-VD/HES-SO - Haute Ecole d'Ingénierie et de Gestion du Canton de Vaud, Route de Cheseaux 1, CH-1401 Yverdon, Switzerland

⁴DIEF-Department of Engineering "Enzo Ferrari", University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, 41125 Modena, Italy

1. Introduction

Soil has been used worldwide to build and today it is still one of the most used construction materials in the world, so much that is estimated that 30% of the global population live in raw earth buildings [1]. The raw earth construction has reached a certain popularity and quality mostly in the region where a suitable soil is available [2, 3]. An appropriate soil needs little to no stabilization and provides a construction material that is durable in the surrounding environment. Traditional raw earth construction techniques [4, 5] evolved into products like the "earth concrete" [6]. Example of earth concretes developed in recent decades are the Alker, the Cast Earth [7] and the Cematerre [8]. Projected soil has been used widely for rendering and constructing walls, as well as for realizing some houses [9]. The typical limitations that hinder the adoption on a larger scale of the classical earth-based concretes include no green strength, clay-dependent mechanical performances, complexity to manage the rheology, high sensibility to water intake and difficult to manage hardening mechanisms. A recent investigation on a sustainable earth-based technology, named "shot-earth" [10], has highlighted the potential of this technology to overcome at once all the mentioned limitations. In addition, the shot-earth technology can transform the excavated soil into a new sustainable and structural building material by satisfying both engineering and environmental needs. In fact, the composition of shot-earth material includes a mixture of excavated soil and aggregates. If the soil is not suitable for the raw-earth construction, a soil stabilization is used. All compounds are mixed together and placed by shooting them at high speed, using a dry process (see Figure 1). This technology can reduce the

Figure 1: In situ spraying process of shot-earth.

exploitation and the logistic of new raw materials and promote more sustainable building processes [11, 12]. From a mechanical point of view, shot-earth has the advantage of an enhanced green strength, i.e. it is self-supporting from the moment it is placed and reach a 28-days strength of about 10 MPa, as well as an elastic modulus of about 9700 MPa. In addition, test repetitions carried out on scale specimens and cores confirmed the regularity of the mechanical characteristics. The research and the recent applications of shot-earth for constructing scale walls showed the potential of this technology as a construction material [10]. Nevertheless, each new construction field might have a different soil, that might imply a new mix-design and a new set of engineering properties. At the present time testing campaigns and new experimental techniques have supplied the data needed by designers. Even though, an easier tool for predicting which engineering properties might be reached using a specific excavated soil in a specific construction field is still needed. In fact, architect and engineers need to know the engineering properties of the materials that they might employ to construct before attempting a preliminary design. For this reason, a methodology to predict the engineering properties of the hardened shot-earth was prepared and is presented in this paper.

The methodology is based on the knowledge of the micro, meso and macro characteristics of the basic components of shot-earth in order to obtain via few tests, on a small quantity of the soil to be excavated in field, the same results than a large testing campaign on both the components of short earth (sand, excavation earth, stabilization) and on hardened shot-earth specimens manufactured with an appropriate pump, in field. The new methodology

that predicts the linear elastic properties of shot-earth is based on the Mori-Tanaka approach [13], which is implemented by adopting a multi-step procedure as proposed by Caporale et al. [14]. The methodology includes the use of the Voight and Reuss bounds and take into consideration the porosity of the medium [15].

Shot-earth is a composite material made with high inclusion of excavated soil (see Figure 2). This inclusion is properly taken into account in the prediction model explained in the following. Despite the large use of earth-based

Figure 2: Shot-earth can be schematized as a porous concrete with soil inclusions.

construction materials, only few papers have been focused on the micromechanics of earth-based composites [13, 16, 17]. None of them investigated the properties on an earthen material placed by shooting like shot-earth. Therefore, all models had to be modified and driving parameters evaluated.

2. Mori-Tanaka homogenization procedure

The Mori-Tanaka method can be applied to investigate the interactions between the phases of a binary composite [18] and predicts its linear elastic mechanical characteristics. The two phases are respectively the inclusions (first constituent) and the matrix (second constituent), in which they are

embedded [19]. It should be remarked that both matrix and inclusions are assumed to be isotropic. Each phase (or component) is characterized by a linear constitutive law of the type:

$$\mathbf{T}^{(i)} = \mathbb{C}^{(i)} \mathbf{E}^{(i)}, \quad (1)$$

for $i = 1, 2$, where $\mathbf{T}^{(i)}$, $\mathbf{E}^{(i)}$ are the stress and strain tensors, respectively. The fourth-order tensor $\mathbb{C}^{(i)}$ is the elasticity tensor. In equation (1), the index i can indicate both the matrix and the inclusions. In particular, the index $i = 1$ specifies the matrix, whereas the inclusions are denoted by $i = 2$. Relation (1) can be rewritten by using the indicial notation in order to introduce the elastic constants $[\mathbb{C}]_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^{(i)}$

$$T_{\alpha\beta}^{(i)} = [\mathbb{C}]_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^{(i)} E_{\gamma\delta}^{(i)}. \quad (2)$$

It is clear that the components of tensor $\mathbb{C}^{(i)}$ for the i -th constituent are expressed in terms of the two mechanical parameters characterizing all isotropic media: the Young's modulus $E^{(i)}$ and the Poisson's ratio $\nu^{(i)}$ [20, 21]. In the following, the components of tensor $\mathbb{C}^{(i)}$ are specified (the components that are not mentioned are null):

$$C_{1111}^{(i)} = C_{2222}^{(i)} = C_{3333}^{(i)} = \frac{E^{(i)} (\nu^{(i)} - 1)}{2 (\nu^{(i)})^2 + \nu^{(i)} - 1}, \quad (3)$$

$$C_{1122}^{(i)} = C_{1133}^{(i)} = C_{2233}^{(i)} = -\frac{E^{(i)} \nu^{(i)}}{2 (\nu^{(i)})^2 + \nu^{(i)} - 1}, \quad (4)$$

$$C_{1313}^{(i)} = C_{2323}^{(i)} = C_{1212}^{(i)} = \frac{E^{(i)}}{2 (1 + \nu^{(i)})} = G^{(i)}, \quad (5)$$

where $G^{(i)}$, for $i = 1, 2$, represent the two shear moduli, which can be expressed as a function of the other two mechanical constants $E^{(i)}$ and $\nu^{(i)}$ [22, 23].

A representative volume element is considered now to establish the average stress tensor $\bar{\mathbf{T}}$ and the average strain tensor $\bar{\mathbf{E}}$

$$\bar{\mathbf{T}} = f_1 \bar{\mathbf{T}}^{(1)} + f_2 \bar{\mathbf{T}}^{(2)}, \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{E}} = f_1 \bar{\mathbf{E}}^{(1)} + f_2 \bar{\mathbf{E}}^{(2)}, \quad (7)$$

in which $\bar{\mathbf{T}}^{(i)}$, $\bar{\mathbf{E}}^{(i)}$ stand for the average stress and strain tensors in the i -th constituent, which are related as follows:

$$\bar{\mathbf{T}}^{(i)} = \mathbb{C}^{(i)} \bar{\mathbf{E}}^{(i)}. \quad (8)$$

On the other hand, f_1, f_2 represent the volume fractions of the two constituents, here considered as the matrix and the inclusions. Given (8), relation (6) becomes

$$\bar{\mathbf{T}} = f_1 \mathbb{C}^{(1)} \bar{\mathbf{E}}^{(1)} + f_2 \mathbb{C}^{(2)} \bar{\mathbf{E}}^{(2)}. \quad (9)$$

The average strains in the i -th constituent can be written in terms of the fourth-order average strain concentration tensor $\mathbb{A}^{(i)}$

$$\bar{\mathbf{E}}^{(i)} = \mathbb{A}^{(i)} \bar{\mathbf{E}}, \quad (10)$$

for $i = 1, 2$. The introduction of this relation into (9) provides the following result:

$$\bar{\mathbf{T}} = (f_1 \mathbb{C}^{(1)} \mathbb{A}^{(1)} + f_2 \mathbb{C}^{(2)} \mathbb{A}^{(2)}) \bar{\mathbf{E}}. \quad (11)$$

The comparison with the global constitutive relation $\bar{\mathbf{T}} = \bar{\mathbb{C}} \bar{\mathbf{E}}$ leads to

$$\bar{\mathbb{C}} = f_1 \mathbb{C}^{(1)} \mathbb{A}^{(1)} + f_2 \mathbb{C}^{(2)} \mathbb{A}^{(2)}, \quad (12)$$

in which $\bar{\mathbb{C}}$ is the overall tensor of elasticity of the composite. Recalling that $\sum_{i=1}^2 f_i \mathbb{A}^{(i)} = \mathbb{I}$, where \mathbb{I} is the fourth-order identity tensor, the overall elasticity tensor assumes the following aspect:

$$\bar{\mathbb{C}} = \mathbb{C}^{(1)} + f_2 (\mathbb{C}^{(2)} - \mathbb{C}^{(1)}) \mathbb{A}^{(2)}. \quad (13)$$

Likewise, the overall compliance tensor $\bar{\mathbb{D}}$ can be defined as well

$$\bar{\mathbb{D}} = \mathbb{D}^{(1)} + f_2 (\mathbb{D}^{(2)} - \mathbb{D}^{(1)}) \mathbb{B}^{(2)}, \quad (14)$$

in which $\mathbb{D}^{(i)}$, for $i = 1, 2$, stands for the compliance tensor of the i -th constituent, whereas $\mathbb{B}^{(i)}$ represents the average stress concentration tensor that allows writing

$$\bar{\mathbb{T}}^{(i)} = \mathbb{B}^{(i)} \bar{\mathbb{T}}. \quad (15)$$

Differently than other approaches, such as the self-consistent based procedures, the Mori-Tanaka homogenization method provides an evaluation of the average fields by considering a finite subregion of the infinite composite as representative volume element [14, 19]. In particular, this method assumes that the average stress tensor of the matrix coincides with the strain tensor evaluated at infinity of the whole composite medium. As illustrated in the papers by Klusemann et al. [19], this assumption allows to compute the strain concentration tensor $\mathbb{A}^{(2)}$ as follows:

$$\mathbb{A}^{(2)} = \mathbb{T} (f_1 \mathbb{I} + f_2 \mathbb{T})^{-1}, \quad (16)$$

where the tensor \mathbb{T} can be defined on the basis of the Eshelby approach for linearly elastic homogeneous bodies with ellipsoidal inclusions [24]

$$\mathbb{T} = \left[\mathbb{I} - \mathbb{S}^{(1)} (\mathbb{C}^{(1)})^{-1} (\mathbb{C}^{(1)} - \mathbb{C}^{(2)}) \right]^{-1}. \quad (17)$$

The Eshelby tensor is denoted by $\mathbb{S}^{(1)}$ and depends on the properties of the matrix [24]. In particular, it is function only of the Poisson's ratio of the matrix $\nu^{(1)}$ and it depends on the aspect ratio of the inclusions [14, 24]. The general procedure for the computation of the Eshelby tensor in the case of linearly elastic homogeneous bodies with isotropic ellipsoidal inclusions is presented in the book by Mura [25]. This procedure can be simplified assuming that the inclusions have spherical shape. In this circumstance, the components of the Eshelby tensor $[\mathbb{S}]_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^{(1)}$ assume closed-form expressions. They are presented below (the components that are not specified are null), recalling its symmetric features

$$S_{1111}^{(1)} = S_{2222}^{(1)} = S_{3333}^{(1)} = \frac{7 - 5\nu^{(1)}}{15(1 - \nu^{(1)})}, \quad (18)$$

$$S_{1122}^{(1)} = S_{2233}^{(1)} = S_{1133}^{(1)} = \frac{5\nu^{(1)} - 1}{15(1 - \nu^{(1)})}, \quad (19)$$

$$S_{1313}^{(1)} = S_{1212}^{(1)} = S_{2323}^{(1)} = \frac{4 - 5\nu^{(1)}}{15(1 - \nu^{(1)})}. \quad (20)$$

Further details concerning the Eshelby tensor can be found in the paper by Shi et al. [26]. On the other hand, the paper by Klusemann et al. [19], can be taken as a reference if non-elliptical inclusions have to be considered.

3. Mechanical features of shot-earth components

The mechanical characterization of the shot-earth as a multi-phase porous hardening material with excavated soil inclusions is made by means of a multi-step application of the Mori- Tanaka scheme. At each step a two-phase composite is considered. The following couples are analyzed (see Figure 2):

- Step 1: Voids (denoted by v) embedded in a pure cement paste (denoted by pp), which provides the porous cement paste (denoted by p);
- Step 2: Aggregate inclusion (denoted by s) embedded in the porous cement paste, which characterizes the mortar (denoted by m);
- Step 3: Shot-earth material defined by excavated soil inclusions (denoted by e) embedded in the mortar.

It should be noted that one of the two components taken into consideration in steps 2 and 3 is the composite obtained in the previous step. The outline of the multi-step procedure is presented in Figure 3. As mentioned above, it should be considered that each constituent is assumed to be isotropic. Therefore, only two independent elastic constants are required for its characterization.

In the first step, the matrix (first component) is the pure cement paste. The pores (or voids), instead, represent the inclusions (second component), which are characterized by a null elastic tensor. The voids are mainly given by the presence of air in the mixture, as well as by the voids left by the evaporation of the water that is bound during the binder hydration. At this stage, the constitutive tensor $\bar{\mathbb{C}}^{(p)}$ of the porous cement paste is computed as

$$\bar{\mathbb{C}}^{(p)} = \mathbb{C}^{(pp)} - f_v \mathbb{C}^{(pp)} \mathbb{A}^{(v)}, \quad (21)$$

where f_v stands for the volume fraction of the pores and it is proportional to the water/cement ratio. Typically, its value is included in the range $0 \div 0.5$, as specified in [14], and it can affect noticeably the overall properties of the final composite.

Figure 3: Chart of the three steps of the homogenization procedure.

The matrix in the second step is given by the porous cement paste, whereas the inclusions are made of aggregates. This mixture represents the mortar, whose constitutive tensor $\bar{\mathbb{C}}^{(m)}$ is defined as

$$\bar{\mathbb{C}}^{(m)} = \mathbb{C}^{(p)} + f_s (\mathbb{C}^{(s)} - \mathbb{C}^{(p)}) \mathbb{A}^{(s)}, \quad (22)$$

where f_s is the volume fraction of the solid components of the composite at this stage.

In the third step, the role of matrix is given to the mortar, whereas the excavated soil represents the inclusions. The so-obtained shot-earth is characterized by the elasticity tensor $\bar{\mathbb{C}}^{(c)}$, which can be evaluated as follows:

$$\bar{\mathbb{C}}^{(c)} = \mathbb{C}^{(m)} + f_e (\mathbb{C}^{(e)} - \mathbb{C}^{(m)}) \mathbb{A}^{(e)}, \quad (23)$$

where f_e stands for the volume fraction of the solid constituents of the composite.

Finally, the constitutive law for the composite material can be expressed as

$$\bar{T}_{\alpha\beta} = [\bar{\mathbb{C}}]_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^{(c)} \bar{E}_{\gamma\delta}, \quad (24)$$

with a form similar to (2). Once the elasticity tensor $\bar{\mathbb{C}}^{(c)}$ of the isotropic body is known, it is possible to compute its elastic features in terms of engineering constants, such as the Young's modulus \bar{E} , the shear modulus \bar{G} , the Poisson's ratio $\bar{\nu}$, and the bulk modulus \bar{K} . The following definitions can be used to this aim [27]:

$$\bar{E} = \frac{\bar{C}_{1111}^2 + \bar{C}_{1111}\bar{C}_{1122} - 2\bar{C}_{1122}^2}{\bar{C}_{1111} + \bar{C}_{1122}}, \quad (25)$$

$$\bar{G} = \frac{\bar{C}_{1111} - \bar{C}_{1122}}{2}, \quad (26)$$

$$\bar{\nu} = \frac{\bar{C}_{1122}}{\bar{C}_{1111} + \bar{C}_{1122}}, \quad (27)$$

$$\bar{K} = \frac{\bar{C}_{1111}^2 + \bar{C}_{1111}\bar{C}_{1122} - 2\bar{C}_{1122}^2}{3\bar{C}_{1111} - 3\bar{C}_{1122}}. \quad (28)$$

Since an isotropic body is characterized by two independent elastic coefficients, the various quantities shown above are not all independent and relationships can be established.

4. Bounds for multi-phase composites

The definitions of the overall constitutive tensors $\bar{\mathbb{C}}$ and $\bar{\mathbb{D}}$ can be used to obtain the bounds for multi-phase composites [28, 29]. These bounds specify the maximum and minimum values of the elastic properties as a function of the constituent volume fractions. The effective properties are included within the upper and lower bounds [30], which define the range of their admissible values. A complete review of the bounding methods is presented by Watt et al. [31].

The upper bound of the elastic features of a multi-phase composite is expressed by the Voigt tensor $\bar{\mathbb{C}}_U$. It can be obtained from equation (13) by setting $\mathbb{A}^{(i)} = \mathbb{I}$, for $i = 1, 2$, as indicated by Klusemann et al. [19]. Consequently, one can assume

$$\bar{\mathbb{C}}_U = \sum_{i=1}^2 f_i \mathbb{C}^{(i)}. \quad (29)$$

By hypothesis, the Voigt bound is also named as isostrain average, since it assumes that each constituent has the same strain, as it can be deduced from (10).

The lower bound of the elastic properties of a multi-phase composite is defined by the Reuss tensor $\bar{\mathbb{C}}_L$. With respect to the Voigt bound, the Reuss bound is known as isostress average since each constituent is characterized by the same stress. In fact, as mentioned in [19], it is assumed that $\mathbb{B}^{(i)} = \mathbb{I}$, for $i = 1, 2$. The current assumption is verified by expression (15). The Reuss tensor $\bar{\mathbb{C}}_L$ can be deduced from definition (14), recalling that the compliance tensor is the inverse of the elasticity tensor

$$\bar{\mathbb{C}}_L = \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 f_i \mathbb{D}^{(i)} \right)^{-1}. \quad (30)$$

The same definitions shown in the previous Section can be applied to the Voigt and Reuss tensors to evaluate the upper and lower bounds in terms of engineering constants, as shown in the book by Mavko et al. [30].

5. Experimental program

In order to predict the shot-earth mechanical properties with the proposed multi-step methodology, the elastic properties of the shot-earth components have to be known. Since the available data found in literature [10] are scarce, an experimental campaign was performed in order to provide missing data. In particular, elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio tests were carried out on the following kinds of specimens:

- Step 1: $40 \times 40 \times 160 \text{ mm}^3$ prisms of porous cement paste. The cement composition used in this step was the same used to fabricate shot-earth in [10], i. e. an ordinary Portland cement;
- Step 2: $\Phi 160 \times \text{H}320 \text{ mm}$ cylinders of cementitious mortar composed by the same cement and aggregates used to fabricate shot-earth.

The aggregate used is a standard 0/8 mm aggregate normally supplied for ordinary concrete. This aggregate is composed by local materials (Western Switzerland) namely a standard sand river 0/4 mm, with a bulk density of about 1400 kg/m^3 , and a gravel 4/8 mm with a bulk density of about 1420 kg/m^3 composed by 25 % and 75 % by weight of crushed and river gravel, respectively;

- Step 3: $\Phi 150 \times H300$ mm cylinders of pressed-earth composed by the same cement, aggregates and excavated soil used to fabricate shot-earth. It should be noted that the excavated soil used in the mixture was locally supplied from a construction site. A standard consolidated triaxial compression test [32] was performed in order to measure the bulk modulus of investigated soil. The testing setup is showed in Figure 4. The triaxial compression test was conducted by applying on the soil-based specimen a differential pressure of 200 kPa for 90 minutes. Such a procedure permits to also observe the time evolution of the volumetric strain until consolidation. The bulk modulus was found to be 2.32 MPa. A particle size analysis of the excavated soil was performed, results are shown in Figure 5. According to the work by Sarro et al. [33], a soil with such a particle size distribution and a bulk modulus of about 2 MPa is expected to have a Young's modulus of about 4 MPa.

It should be noted that for steps 1 and 2 the fraction ratio of cement and aggregates was the same one adopted in shot-earth recipe investigated in [10]. Instead, for step 3 the amount of excavated soil inclusion was varied in order to consider the effect of its volume fraction on the elastic properties of shot-earth. In all steps the specimens were prepared by homogenizing the

Figure 4: Standard consolidated triaxial compression test performed on excavated soil specimen according to [32].

Figure 5: Particle size curve of excavated soil used to make specimens of step 3.

components in a rotating pan mixer (see stage 1 in Figure 6). After five minutes of mixing, the mixture was poured in a steel formwork. In regard to specimens of step 1 (porous cement paste) and 2 (cementitious mortar), specimens of step 3 (shot-earth) were also compacted with a mechanical hydraulic press, (see Figure 6 stage 6). The compaction pressure was about 5 MPa. Then, the specimen was demolded and protected with a plastic sheet in order to slow down the water evaporation. After 28 days of curing under controlled conditions ($20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, $60\% \pm 5\% \text{RH}$) the specimens were prepared to be mechanically tested. A Walter & Bai hydraulic press 500 kN was used to test both the Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio of specimens of steps 1, 2 and 3. Tests were conducted according to the well established standard protocol [34, 35]. For the Poisson's ratio the test set up showed in Figure 7 was prepared to fit the geometry and size of the pressed-earth specimens. Table 1 summarizes the relevant results collected during the experimental campaign.

Figure 6: Stage 1: Rotation panel mixer used to make composite specimens. Stage 2: Check of workability level by a visual examination of the mixture, according to the protocol used by practitioners. Stage 3: Equipment for molding, compacting and demolding specimens of step 3. Stage 4: Inserting of the fresh mixture of step 3 within a steel form-work by setting five layers of homogeneous thick one above the other. Stage 5: Compacting each layer with a given stress level. Stage 6: Demolding specimens of step 3. Stage 7: Visual examination of specimens before curing.

Table 1: Experimental results.

Description	Constituents	Young's modulus $E^{(i)}$ (GPa)	Poisson's ratio $\nu^{(i)}$
Step 1	Porous cement past	8.38 ± 0.68	0.23 ± 0.01
Step 2	Mortar	27.97 ± 0.45	0.20 ± 0.03
	Shot-earth 2/7/2	23.02 ± 0.82	0.23 ± 0.03
Step 3	Shot-earth 7/7/2	9.71 ± 0.78	0.15 ± 0.03
	Shot-earth 10/7/2	7.25 ± 0.25	0.15 ± 0.03

Figure 7: Experimental test performed on specimens of steps 1 (a), 2(b) and 3(c), measuring Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio according to [34] and [35] respectively.

6. Analytical results

The multi-step Mori-Tanaka approach, presented in Section 2 provides a prediction of the mechanical properties of a binary composite. Hence in step 1 the model was applied several times to a cement-voids composite with different proportion between voids and cement paste. The results presented in Table 2 are computed, as suggested by Caporale et al. [14], using a Young's modulus $E^{(pp)} = 15$ GPa and a Poisson's ratio $\nu^{(pp)} = 0.22$. Experimental results of step 1 (see Table 2 and Figure 3) match the analytical results for a porosity of 0.25 – 0.3, a value coherent with the findings of [14]. Table 2 also highlights the importance of the quantity of voids on the mechanical characteristics.

The Mori-Tanaka model was then applied for a binary composite having as components the cement paste with voids analyzed in step 1 and the aggregate. This binary mix can be viewed as a ternary mix having the third component equal to zero. Shot-earth is a ternary mix whose volume fractions are given as: cement / aggregate / soil. A typical mix for a structural shot-earth is 2/7/7. In step 2 the mix proportion is 2/7/0 while in step 3 will be 2/7/ x , where x is a variable quantity of excavated soil assuming the values of 0, 7 and 10. In step 3 as in all steps a binary composite is analyzed using the Mori-Tanaka approach. The composite is made by adding to the mortar calculated in step 2 (made of cement paste with voids and aggregates) the excavated soil. Thus, in step 3, it is important to know the proportion between cement paste f'_p , aggregate f'_s , and excavated soil f'_e , whose values are calculated as follows:

$$f'_p = \frac{2}{7+2+x}, \quad f'_s = \frac{7}{7+2+x}, \quad f'_e = \frac{x}{7+2+x}. \quad (31)$$

Table 2: Mechanical properties at step 1 of the porous cement past. Comparison with the experiment varying the volume fraction of voids f_v .

	$E^{(p)}$ (GPa)	$G^{(p)}$ (GPa)	$K^{(p)}$ (GPa)
Experiment	8.38	3.41*	5.17*
Analytical	$f_v = 0.00$	15.000	6.148
	$f_v = 0.05$	13.570	5.567
	$f_v = 0.10$	12.270	5.038
	$f_v = 0.15$	11.083	4.554
	$f_v = 0.20$	9.995	4.110
	$f_v = 0.25$	8.995	3.701
	$f_v = 0.30$	8.072	3.323
	$f_v = 0.35$	7.217	2.973

* $G^{(p)}$, $K^{(p)}$ are evaluated analytically by using the Poisson's ratio $\nu^{(p)} = 0.23$ obtained experimentally.

It can be noted that the proportions depend on the quantity of excavated soil (denoted by x) inserted in the mixture. As shown in [14], the volume fractions of the solids components f_s and f_e can be computed as follows:

$$f_s = \frac{f'_s}{f'_s + f'_p}, \quad f_e = \frac{f'_e}{f'_e + f'_s + f'_p}. \quad (32)$$

In step 2 a Young's modulus $E^{(s)} = 45$ GPa and Poisson's ratio $\nu^{(s)} = 0.23$ were employed to compute the mechanical properties of the binary composite made combining the cement paste with voids and the aggregate. These values for $E^{(s)}$ and $\nu^{(s)}$ are coherent with the literature [36, 37, 38]. In step 3 the composite obtained in step 2 was combined with the excavated soil to predict the properties of a shot-earth characterized by volume proportions $2/7/x$. The calculations were made using, for the soil fraction, the Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio determined experimentally. Step 3 provided three sets of results for three different shot-earth mixtures characterized by volume proportions of $2/7/x$ where x assumed the values 0, 7 and 10, respectively. During the experimental campaign shot-earth specimens were produced using the same three mixes. Test results are compared with the multi-step Mori-Tanaka predictions obtained modeling the inclusions as spherical. In Figures 8, 9 and 10 the experimental values and model predictions are presented. Figures also show the variation of the Young's modulus \bar{E} , shear modulus \bar{G} and bulk modulus \bar{K} as a function of the volume fraction f_e and as a function of the volume fraction of the porosity f_v . The upper and lower bounds are depicted in all graphs. Reuss (lower) bound is low since this specific soil is a weak construction material and therefore its mechanical characteristics have a much lower value than the mortar. It can be observed that the analytical results predicted by the Mori-Tanaka approach are close

Figure 8: Evaluation of the Young's modulus \bar{E} of the composite as a function of the volume fraction f_e , for different values of the porosity f_v . The inclusions are modeled as spherical.

Figure 9: Evaluation of the shear modulus \bar{G} of the composite as a function of the volume fraction f_e , for different values of the porosity f_v . The inclusions are modeled as spherical.

Figure 10: Evaluation of the bulk modulus \bar{K} of the composite as a function of the volume fraction f_e , for different values of the porosity f_v . The inclusions are modeled as spherical.

to the experimental values and therefore the model can predict the elastic properties of shot-earth. Consequently, once the properties of shot-earth components are known, especially those of soil inclusions, it can be possible identify which kind of civil engineering applications might be made with a specific excavation soil. It should be also highlighted that the choice of the aggregate's properties made in this study is correct since the prediction of the mechanical properties of the composite for $f_e = 0$ matches the experimental values. It should be recalled that $f_e = 0$ defines the second step of the procedure as defined in the previous Sections. Figures 8, 9 and 10 show also, as expected, the importance of the porosity taken into account through f_v : an increasing value of the porosity affects the mechanical properties. Furthermore, as expected, for $f_v = 0.25 - 0.3$ the best agreement between the analytical results and the experimental properties is obtained.

7. Final remarks

In [10] a new sustainable material called shot-earth is presented. Shot-earth is made of excavated soil, aggregate and, if needed, a binder for stabilization. Excavation soil can have much different characteristics according to the location of the construction site. Consequently, a practical method to predict which civil engineering applications are possible with a specific soil is needed, by minimizing the costs of both field trial and the equipment requested. The proposed methodology can be applied a priori, before the realization of the construction in a specified location. Its aim, in fact, is the preliminary evaluation of the mechanical properties of the shot-earth material that could be obtained by using the soil which is excavated from that

particular site. In this paper, the shot-earth is modeled as a multi-phase material and an analytical procedure based on a multi-step application of the Mori-Tanaka approach has been used to predict its mechanical properties. The model is simple to use and can predict the elastic modulus, shear modulus and bulk modulus of shot earth as a function of the volume fraction of shot-earth components and of the porosity. The predictions of the model were validated by means of a wide experimental campaign.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The raw/processed data required to reproduce these findings cannot be shared at this time as the data also forms part of an ongoing study.

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